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Abstract: Nuclear power plants can operate with single-circuit, double-circuit and triple-circuit coolant. A single-circuit scheme is used in nuclear power plants with channel-type reactors. In such nuclear power plants, the coolant is also the working fluid. In them, the boiling reactor itself is a steam generator, therefore the entire scheme is radioactive. It is surrounded by biological protection.

Keywords: nuclear power plant, circuit, cooling system, working, station, reactor, steam, generator, scheme, radioactive, biological.

A nuclear power plant is a power plant that belongs to the thermal power plant type in terms of its technological scheme. While conventional thermal power plants (TPPs) burn coal, oil, fuel oil (fuel oil), and gas, a nuclear power plant uses uranium as fuel. The main part of a nuclear power plant is a nuclear boiler, that is, a nuclear reactor. In a nuclear power plant, most often, nuclear reactors. 4 types are used:

- 1) Water-water (in which ordinary water is used both as a moderator and as a heat carrier);
- 2) Graphite-water (water is a heat carrier, and graphite is a heat carrier);
- 3) Heavy water (ordinary water is a heat carrier, and heavy water is a heat carrier);

4) Graphite-gas (gas is a heat carrier, graphite is a heat carrier).

Modern nuclear power mainly uses uranium-235. Its natural reserves are not very large, and it makes up only 10% of organic fuel. This amount cannot provide nuclear power with fuel for a long time. There are sufficient reserves of uranium-238 and thorium-232 in the earth's crust, which are raw materials for obtaining plutonium-239 and uranium-233, which are used as nuclear fuel. A double-circuit scheme is used in nuclear power plants with pressurized water reactors. In such nuclear power plants, water is supplied to the reactor core under pressure, which is heated. The energy of the coolant is used to create saturated steam in a steam generator. The primary circuit is radioactive and is surrounded by biological protection (except when an inert gas is used as a coolant). The second circuit is generally radiation-safe, since the working fluid and coolant of the first circuit do not come into contact. The three-circuit scheme is used in nuclear power plants with fast neutron reactors with sodium coolant. To prevent radioactive sodium from coming into contact with water, a second circuit is built with non-radioactive sodium. Thus, the scheme turns out to be three-circuit. A distinctive feature of nuclear power plants with fast neutron reactors is that, while generating electricity and heat, they simultaneously produce fissile isotopes suitable for use in thermal nuclear reactors.

Figure 1. The largest nuclear power plant in the world.

The advantages of nuclear power plants include:

-electricity generation is cheap;

- a 1000 MW gas-fired thermal power plant emits 13 thousand tons of harmful substances into the atmosphere per year, and a coal-fired thermal power plant emits 165 thousand tons of harmful substances. A 1000 MW thermal power plant absorbs 8 million tons of oxygen per year. A nuclear power plant does not consume oxygen and does not emit harmful emissions as mentioned above;

- there is no need to build them near a large fuel source. Bringing coal and gas to a thermal power plant requires significant costs, while the uranium needed for a nuclear power plant can fit in one truck;

- spent fuel is reprocessed and used again as fuel;

- high power: the power of one power unit is 1000-1600 MW.

Nuclear power plants have the following disadvantages:

- irradiated fuel is dangerous, its processing and storage is a complex process and requires a lot of money;

- A large amount of money and a lot of water are needed to build a nuclear power plant;

- A nuclear power plant emits a large amount of radioactive waste and requires a large infrastructure to store it;

- The probability of an accident with a nuclear power plant is extremely low, but if one does happen, it can lead to serious consequences.

CONCLUSION

One of the advantages of nuclear power plants over conventional thermal power plants is their high environmental friendliness, which is maintained during the competent operation of nuclear reactors. Existing radiation safety barriers of nuclear power plants (fuel element cladding, nuclear reactor vessels, etc.) prevent

contamination of the coolant with radioactive decay products. Nuclear power plants are almost always built near energy consumers. They are built on the lower side of the nearest settlement. A sanitary protection zone and a monitoring zone are being established around the plant, where the population is prohibited. Monitoring and measuring equipment are placed in the monitoring zone for continuous monitoring of the environment. The ability of nuclear power plants to operate for a long time without changing fuel allows them to be used even in remote areas. The operating life of a nuclear power plant is 25-30 years.

REFERENCES:

1. <https://kun.uz/news/2018/10/22/atom-elektr-stansiyasi>.
2. PRIS - Permanently Shutdown Reactors Archived, May 2, 2019
3. Wayback Machine, International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA).
4. Margulova T.Kh. Podushko L.A. Nuclear Power Plants - Textbook.
5. Denisov V.P. Dragunov Yu.G. VVER Reactor Plants for Nuclear